

Informing the operation of intelligent automated intra-row weeding machines in direct-sown sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.): Crop effects of hoeing and flaming across early growth stages, tool working distances, and intensities.

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Abstract The effective management of intra-row weeds is necessary to preserve crop yields in direct-seeded sugar beet; however, suitable options for effective control using direct non-chemical strategies are limited. The advent of automated intelligent intra-row weeding machines provided a promising solution. These machines can identify individual crop plants, then selectively hoeing or flaming the between-crop zone within the intra-row while leaving the close-to-crop zone untreated. As automated intra-row weeding technologies advance, their ability to operate accurately in close proximity to the crop will continue to improve. It is, therefore, necessary to consider the crop's tolerance to weeding when dictating optimal working distances between tool and crop across early growth stages. This information may also inform the development of automated intra-row weeders by defining the level of precision at which they should be capable of operating. Results from five pot experiments in this study indicate that hoeing can be implemented as close as 1 cm from the center of sugar plants, from cotyledon through the four-leaf stage, without causing adverse crop effects. Furthermore, sugar beet tolerance to direct flaming increased with crop growth stage, and flaming at an 88% lethal propane dose of 3.72 kg km⁻¹ was tolerated at distances 1.5 cm and greater at the two-leaf stage.

Keywords flame weeding; intra-row hoeing; intra-row weed control; crop tolerance; flaming tolerance; hoeing tolerance.

Introduction

Sugar beets (*Beta vulgaris* L.) are particularly vulnerable to crop yield and quality losses resulting from competition with weeds. As crop-weed proximity decreases, yield losses increase. For example, in sugar beet, Heisel et al. (2002) observed a 20% reduction in yield when the distance between crop plants and weed species, wild mustard (*Sinapis arvensis* L.) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), decreased from 8 to 2 cm. Sugar beets also possess a slow growth rate throughout early development, making them sensitive to competition from weeds emerging before, concurrently with, or soon after the crop (Kropff, 1998; Kropff et al., 1992). Yield losses resulting from competition with 5 plants m⁻² of common lambsquarters (*Chenopodium album* L.) emerging on the same date as a sugar beet crop versus ten days after were reported as 79 and 37%, respectively (Kropff & Spitters, 1991). Therefore, to mitigate yield loss in sugar beet, it is necessary to control weeds growing nearest the crop, within the intra-row zone, across early growth stages.

While effective weed control in the inter-row zone of sugar beet is attainable using direct non-chemical methods (Tillet et al., 2002), non-chemical control of intra-row weeds is arguably much more challenging because of the crop's presence. It is difficult to effectively control weeds in the intra-row zone of sugar beet without causing crop damages that could negatively affect yield. Non-intelligent cultivators designed to operate in the intra-row are available; for example, hoe ridgers, finger weeders, torsion weeders, rotary hoes, and harrows (Bleeker et al., 2002; Champagne, 2022). These devices treat crop plants and weeds uniformly, requiring a substantial size differential between a larger crop and smaller weeds to operate selectively, maximizing weed control while minimizing crop damage (Gallandt et al., 2018). Because sugar beets are slow to establish, this prerequisite is challenging to achieve in a direct-seeded crop. Sugar beet is also sensitive to damages resulting from disturbance throughout early growth; thus, it is recommended to avoid direct cultivation until the four- to six-leaf stage (Bleeker et al., 2002; Melander, 2000). Transplanting sugar beets would help establish an ideal crop-weed size differential; however, this practice is far more labor intensive than direct seeding and may negatively impact crop quality (Melander, 2000). As a result of the aforementioned constraints, hand weeding remains a necessary but costly weed management strategy for controlling intra-row weeds in sugar beet (Ascard et al., 1995).

Intelligent automated weeding machines provide a promising solution for non-chemical control of weeds established within the crop row. These devices can identify individual crop plants and selectively treat the between-crop zone within the intra-row using cultivators or flame

weeders while leaving the close-to-crop zone untreated (Machleb et al., 2020). Machine vision and global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) predominate as the leading methods of crop detection employed amongst automated intra-row weeders currently on the market (Machleb et al., 2020; Melander & McCollough, 2021). Intra-row weeders employing machine vision systems currently rely on a crop-weed size differential to distinguish larger crop plants from smaller weeds (Melander et al., 2015). In a transplanted crop, where a significant size disparity is present, these automated weeders are capable of operating within the intra-row zone to selectively kill weeds without reducing crop stand or yield (Lati et al., 2016). Whereas, in a direct-seeded crop, stand reduction during operation is likely if crop plants are too small to achieve accurate detection (Lati et al., 2016). The identification of direct-seeded sugar beet thus poses a significant challenge for intelligent intra-row weeders employing machine vision systems, especially across early growth stages when weed control is of utmost importance from a yield preservation perspective. Progress has reportedly been made, however, in the ability of machine vision systems to detect direct-seeded crops via shape recognition, even at high weed pressure, instead of relying on size differential; this advancement in machine vision technology may soon enable accurate intra-row operation as early as the two-leaf growth stage in sugar beet. Intelligent weeders employing GNSS systems achieve intra-row crop detection via seed mapping, recording the precise location of individual crop plants at the time of direct seeding (Machleb et al., 2020; Melander & McCollough, 2021). Because this method does not really rely on crop plants' physical presence to pinpoint their location in the field, it permits operation before and immediately after crop emergence, enabling direct intra-row weeding during early growth. However, one drawback of this strategy is that GNSS systems cannot identify where crop plants failed to establish; thus, in instances where there are gaps in the crop row, weeding will not occur in the area defined close-to-crop zone where crop plants are absent.

The development of intelligent intra-row weeding machines capable of operating in direct-seeded row crops constitutes a significant advancement for non-chemical weed management. The ability of these intelligent weeding machines to operate precisely, in close proximity to direct-seeded crops and across early growth stages is only expected to improve in the near future. However, it must be considered that a trade-off exists when reducing the working distance between a hoeing or flaming implement and crop plants; yield losses resulting from physical damages and yield benefits associated with removing weeds growing nearest the crop are at odds with one another. Thus, this study aims to inform the development and operation of automated intra-row weeding machines in direct seeded sugar beet by: (i) determining the distance at which hoeing can be performed without inflicting significant crop

damages across early growth, cotyledon through four-leaf stage; (ii) determining the intensity at which flaming can be implemented without inflicting significant crop damages across early growth, cotyledon through six-leaf stage; and (iii) determine the proximity at which a 'lethal flaming dose' can be administered at the two-leaf growth stage without inflicting significant crop damages. Ultimately, this information may be used to optimize the selectivity of automated intra-row weeding machines, allowing flaming and hoeing to occur at intensities as high as possible and at proximities as close as possible in order to maximize weed kill while minimizing crop damages. Crop damages are expected to increase as hoeing and flaming distance decrease and as flaming intensity increases. It is also expected that sugar beet tolerance to weeding tools will increase as they grow; thus, damages resulting from flaming and hoeing will be greater when implemented at earlier crop growth stages.

Materials and Methods

Design of Experiments and Treatment Specifications

Five pot experiments were performed at the Aarhus University Flakkebjerg Research Center (Slagelse, Denmark; 55.33°N, 11.39°E), evaluating the response of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L., cv. Davinci) to hoeing and flaming, when implemented across early growth stages and at varying proximities or intensities. Hoeing distance experiments ($EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}$) studied the effect of hoeing proximity across early growth stages, flaming intensity experiments ($EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}$) studied the effect of flaming dose across early growth stages when distance was held constant, and flaming distance experiment ($EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE}$) studied the effect of flaming proximity when dose and growth stage were held constant. $EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}$ and $EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}$ experiments were replicated once in 2019 and once in 2020; $EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}$ was performed once in 2021 only. Table 1 summarizes dates and sugar beet growth stages when performing key treatments within each experiment.

All sugar beets were planted in a growing medium possessing a sand soil texture (90% sand, 4% silt, 6% clay), consisting of a 2:1 mixture by volume of field soil (sourced from Slagelse, Denmark 55.32°N, 11.40°E) and sand (sourced from Dalmoose Vognmandsforretning ApS, Lundsgårdsvej 5, DK-4261, Dalmoose). Soils were combined using a portable concrete mixer (ATIKA Profi 145, ATIKA GmbH, Ahlen, Germany) and were fertilized uniformly with YaraMila 24-4-10 (DLG, Axelborg, Vesterbrogade 4A, DK-1620, Copenhagen V, Denmark) at a rate of 200 kg of nitrogen ha^{-1} ; thus, fertilizer application rates were based on the exposed soil surface area of growing containers.

When planting sugar beets, a template system was used to ensure consistent sowing depth and position at the center of each container. Planting templates were made of prefinished plywood cut to fit snugly into container openings. After filling containers with soil, seeds were sown through a hole positioned at the center of the template. A consistent sowing depth was achieved by passing a plunger with a fixed stopper through the planting hole, pushing seeds 2 cm into the soil. Two seeds were planted in each container to improve the likelihood of establishment. Following emergence, sugar beets were thinned to one seedling per container. Throughout experimentation, any germinant weeds that established within containers were removed immediately.

EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE} investigated two factors in a randomized full factorial design with four replications per year: (i) hoeing distance at six levels, 0 (HD₀), 1 (HD₁), 2 (HD₂₀), 3 (HD₃₀), 4 (HD₄), and 5 cm (HD₅) relative to the center of sugar beet plants, and (ii) crop growth stage at time of hoeing at three levels, cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), first pair of true leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), and second pair of true leaves unfolded (CS₁₄). One untreated control treatment was also included within each block (HD_{CTRL}). Sugar beets were grown in rectangular containers possessing a length, width, and height of 180, 245, and 68 mm, respectively. Experiments were performed under semi-field conditions, that is, in boxes kept outdoors, underneath a polycarbonate roof with open sides. Containers were watered uniformly via manual controls. In 2019, two drip emitters were installed per box, dispensing 2L of water per hour when turned on; in 2020, flood tables were used to irrigate. Hoeing treatments were implemented on all four sides of potted sugar beet plants (Supplementary Video 1), simulating the disturbance pattern caused by the intelligent automated intra-row weeder, the Robovator (www.visionweeding.com). F. Poulsen Engineering ApS designed the hoeing simulator used to implement treatments within growing containers. (Havlsoe, Denmark). The hoeing simulator was comprised of a 3 cm long side knife propelled forward by a compressed air pneumatic cylinder at a speed of 1.4 km h⁻¹. Across all treatments, hoeing was performed at a depth of 2 cm.

EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} also studied two factors in a randomized full factorial design with four replications per year: (i) flame weeding intensity at six levels, 0.1 (FI_{0.1}), 0.2 (FI_{0.2}), 0.4 (FI_{0.4}), 0.8 (FI_{0.8}), 1.6 (FI_{1.6}), and 3.4 (FI_{3.4}) seconds of flaming exposure to sugar beet plants, and (ii) crop growth stage at time of flaming at three levels, CS₁₂, CD₁₄, and third pair of true leaves unfolded (CD₁₆) in 2019 and CD₁₀, CD₁₂, and CD₁₄ in 2020. Crop growth stage treatments differ among experimental years due to a logistical error, whereby the opportunity to flame weed at CD₁₀ was missed in 2019; therefore, treatments were deferred one growth stage. One untreated control treatment was also included within each block (FI_{CTRL}). Sugar beets were grown in two-liter

round pots under the same semi-field conditions described for EXP_{HOE}. While irrigation was controlled separately for EXP_{HOE} and EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}, identical irrigation systems were used to water pots in 2019 and 2020; the only exception being that one drip emitter was installed per pot in 2019. Flame weeding treatments were implemented twice per pot in sequence and on opposite sides of the plant. Flaming treatments were implemented with an experimental flaming simulator built from a ROBOVATOR thermal weeding unit (F. Poulsen Engineering ApS., Havlsøe, Denmark) augmented so that a single flaming nozzle could be activated for precise intervals of time (Supplementary Video 2). Across all EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} treatments, flame-emitting nozzle height was 7.5 cm, and flame angle was 50° relative to the soil's surface. Flaming distance, the point at which the flame made contact with the soil's surface, was held constant at 2 cm relative to the center of sugar beet plants. In EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}, the flame was aimed at crop plants to study crop tolerance to direct flaming when flaming dose increased and flaming distance was constant.

EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE} studied only one factor in a randomized complete block design with eight replications: (i) flaming distance at ten levels, 0.0 (FD_{0.0}), 0.5 (FD_{0.5}), 1.0 (FD_{1.0}), 1.5 (FD_{1.5}), 2.0 (FD_{2.0}), 2.5 (FD_{2.5}), 3.0 (FD_{3.0}), 3.5 (FD_{3.5}), and 4.0 cm (FD_{4.0}), as well as an untreated control treatment (FD_{CTRL}). Sugar beets were grown under glass-house conditions in two-liter round pots on flood tables, receiving uniform watering via manual controls. Treatments were implemented using the same flaming simulator and set up as was described for EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}. However, at FD_{0.0} the flame's contact point with the soil's surface was centered on the crop plant, and flaming distance increased perpendicular to the theoretical crop row; this allowed for the evaluation of flaming distance when flaming dose and crop growth stage were held constant. All flaming treatments were performed on the same day (Table 1) in an attempt to treat sugar beet plants at the two-leaf growth stage uniformly. However, on the day of flaming treatment, 8%, 29%, 18%, and 46% of sugar beets were observed to be at cotyledon, two-leaf, three-leaf, and four-leaf growth stages, respectively; this variation was accounted for during analysis. Flaming duration was held constant across all EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE} treatments at 2.0 seconds; this flaming duration was chosen as a 'lethal dose' upon referencing EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} results from 2019 and 2020, it was also considered that FD_{0.0} would receive a direct hit by the flame.

Data collection

Upon sugar beet harvest in EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}, EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}, and EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE}, leaves were dissected from the roots at the soil's surface and laid flat, without any overlapping, beneath a transparent vinyl sheet. Digital photos were taken from above the broken-down shoot

components and analyzed to determine the final leaf area using Easy Leaf Area software (SciPy Developers 2013, University of California, Los Angeles, California, United States; Easlon & Bloom, 2014). Soil was rinsed from the roots, then blow- and above-ground components were dried separately for 24 hours at a temperature of 80°C and weighed to acquire dry matter measurements of both root and shoot biomass (g).

In EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}, before implementing each hoeing treatment, soil moisture, as a measure of volumetric water content (%), was measured with a HydroSense II Handheld Soil Moisture Sensor (Campbell Scientific Inc., North Logan, UT, USA). In EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} and EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE}, when carrying out flaming treatments, the maximum achieved temperature (°C) at the center of the sugar beet plant was measured using a FLIR ONE™ Gen 2 thermal imaging camera (FLIR® Systems Inc., Wilsonville, OR, United States). Thermal imaging camera temperature approximation was validated by obtaining a reading of the temperature of boiling water (100°C). In EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE}, a non-destructive measure of leaf area (cm²) was acquired on the day of flaming treatment; digital photos were taken from above each plant and analyzed using Easy Leaf Area software.

Data analyses

Data were analyzed using JMP® software (version PRO 16.1.0, SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA). Across experiments, $\log_{10}(x+1)$ and square root $(x+1)$ transformations were made when necessary to satisfy test assumptions of equality of variance among residuals and the normal distribution of residuals. EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE} data from 2019 and 2020 were analyzed separately. Because HD_{CTRL} was not included in the full factorial design, separate models were used to evaluate main effects and interactions and to perform pre-planned contrasts. With HD_{CTRL} excluded from analysis, a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate main effects and interactions among experimental factors, hoeing distance (HD), and crop stage (CS). Mixed model variables included the random term, block, and fixed terms, CS, HD, and CS*HD. With HD_{CTRL} included in the analysis, a one-way ANOVA was used to carry out pre-planned contrasts. Mixed model variables included the random term, block, and one fixed term, treatment, comprised of all 18 unique combinations of HD and CS represented in experiments and the untreated control group, HD_{CTRL}. Contrasts compared each unique combination of HD and CS to HD_{CTRL}. Soil moisture at the time of hoeing was assessed for its effect on treatment outcomes. No relationship was observed between the continuous variable, soil volumetric water content (%), and response variables, sugar beet final leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, or total biomass; therefore, soil moisture was not included in the model. The same methodology

was used to analyze $EXP_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$ as was described for $EXP_{\text{HOE.DISTANCE}}$; however, with the experimental factor, flame intensity (FI) was assessed in place of HD.

In the analysis of $EXP_{\text{FLAME.DISTANCE}}$, FD_{CTRL} was included within the full factorial design; therefore, a single model was used to assess treatment effects, and to perform pre-planned contrasts. With FD_{CTRL} included in the analysis, a one-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was carried out. Mixed model variables included the random term, block, the fixed term, and treatment, comprised of all nine flaming distances (FD) tested as well as the untreated control group, HD_{CTRL} , and the continuous term, leaf area (cm^2), measured on the day of implementing flaming treatments, as a co-variate assuming a linear relationship between leaf area and the response variable. Contrasts compared each level of FD to HD_{CTRL} .

Oxygen and propane fuel consumption per linear km of crop row (kg km^{-1}) were estimated for the ROBOVATOR flame weeder among all treatments studied in $EXP_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$ and $EXP_{\text{FLAME.DISTANCE}}$ (Table 2). Calculations were based on ROBOVATOR specifications; two bars outfitted with 30 flame-emitting nozzles each operate together when working within the intra-row zone, and there's a 4 cm distance between nozzles. An intra-row crop spacing of 15 cm between sugar beet plants was also assumed. Measures of ROBOVATOR fuel and oxygen flow were acquired using an AWM5102 Airflow Sensor (Honeywell International Inc., Houston, TX, USA). A single flaming nozzle used approximately 1.0 L min^{-1} of propane and 0.87 L min^{-1} of oxygen. In both $EXP_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$ and $EXP_{\text{FLAME.DISTANCE}}$, the absolute pressure of propane and oxygen were held constant across treatments at 1.15 and 1.21 bar, respectively.

Results

Hoeing Distance

When each of the $EXP_{\text{HOE.DISTANCE}}$ treatments were compared to the untreated control (HD_{CTRL}), the following contrasts were significant ($p < 0.05$). Final sugar beet leaf area (cm^2) was reduced at $CS_{10} HD_0$ by 76% in 2020, at $CS_{12} HD_0$ by 53% in 2019 and 82% in 2020, and at $CS_{14} HD_0$ by 100% in 2019 and 60% in 2020 (Figure 1, Tables 3 and 4). Total sugar beet biomass (g) was reduced at $CS_{10} HD_0$ by 78% in 2020, at $CS_{12} HD_0$ by 93% in 2019 and 90% in 2020, and at $CS_{14} HD_0$ by 95% in 2019 and 58% in 2020 (Figure 1, Tables 3 and 4). Sugar beet root biomass (g) was reduced at $CS_{10} HD_0$ by 69% in 2020, at $CS_{12} HD_0$ by 95% in 2019 and 93% in 2020, and at $CS_{14} HD_0$ by 100% in 2019 and 65% in 2020 (Tables 3 and 4). Sugar beet shoot biomass (g) was reduced at $CS_{10} HD_0$ by 84% in 2020, at $CS_{12} HD_0$ by 91% in 2019 and 88% in 2020, and at $CS_{14} HD_0$ by 90% in 2019 and 55% in 2020 (Tables 3 and 4).

Across crop growth stages tested, final sugar beet leaf area at HD₀ was on average 72% less than all other hoeing distances in 2019 and 47% less than HD₁, HD₄, and HD₅ in 2020. Total sugar beet biomass at HD₀ was on average 45% less than all other hoeing distances in 2019 and was 24% less in 2020. Across hoeing distances tested, sugar beet root biomass across CS₁₂ and CS₁₄ were on average 11% less than CS₁₀.

Sugar beet mortality rate was 50% at CS₁₀ HD₀ and 25% at CS₁₀ HD₁ in 2020 (data not shown). In both years, 50% of sugar beet plants were killed at CS₁₂ HD₀, and 100% and 25% were killed at CS₁₄ HD₀ in 2019 and 2020, respectively. A 100% survival rate was observed across all other treatments. Although some plants survived being hit directly with the hoeing simulator, resulting physical damages caused taproot forking in all surviving sugar beets receiving HD₀ (data not shown). No forking of the taproot was observed in any other hoeing distance treatments tested (HD₁, HD₂, HD₃, HD₄, or HD₅).

Flaming Intensity

The average maximum temperatures achieved at the center of the sugar beet plants during treatment for each flaming intensity studied were 30.6°C (±1.1) at Fl_{0.1}, 45.2°C (±3.4) at Fl_{0.2}, 65.6°C (±4.6) at Fl_{0.4}, 69.2°C (±5.6) at Fl_{0.8}, 80.0°C (±6.0) at Fl_{1.6}, 97.1°C (±5.6) at Fl_{3.2}. When each of the EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} treatments were compared to the untreated control (Fl_{CTRL}), the following contrasts were significant (p < 0.05). In 2020, final sugar beet leaf area was reduced by 36% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.2}, and by 100% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.4}, CS₁₀ Fl_{0.8}, CS₁₀ Fl_{1.6}, and CS₁₀ Fl_{3.2} (Figure 2, Table 6). Final sugar beet leaf area was also reduced at CS₁₂ Fl_{0.8} by 56% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{1.6} by 55% in 2019 and 93% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{3.2} by 100% in 2019 and 2020, at CS₁₄ Fl_{1.6} by 67% in 2020, and at CS₁₄ Fl_{3.2} by 100% in 2020. In 2020, total sugar beet biomass was reduced by 98% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.4} and by 100% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.8}, CS₁₀ Fl_{1.6}, and CS₁₀ Fl_{3.2} (Figure 2, Tables 5 and 6). Total sugar beet biomass was also reduced at CS₁₂ Fl_{0.8} by 60% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{1.6} by 68% in 2019 and 89% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{3.2} by 80% in 2019 and 98% in 2020, at CS₁₄ Fl_{1.6} by 53% in 2020, and at CS₁₄ Fl_{3.2} by 74% in 2020. In 2020, sugar beet root biomass was reduced by 99% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.4} and 100% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.8}, CS₁₀ Fl_{1.6}, and CS₁₀ Fl_{3.2}. Sugar beet root biomass was also reduced at CS₁₂ Fl_{0.8} by 64% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{1.6} by 74% in 2019 and 96% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{3.2} by 64% in 2019 and 97% in 2020, at CS₁₄ Fl_{1.6} by 62% in 2020, and at CS₁₄ Fl_{3.2} by 91% in 2020 (Tables 5 and 6). In 2020, sugar beet shoot biomass was reduced by 98% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.4}, 99% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.8}, and 100% at CS₁₀ Fl_{1.6} and CS₁₀ Fl_{3.2}. Sugar beet shoot biomass was also reduced at CS₁₂ Fl_{0.8} by 56% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{1.6} by 62% in 2019 and 85% in 2020, at CS₁₂ Fl_{3.2} by 99% in 2019 and 2020, at CS₁₄ Fl_{1.6} by 49% in 2020, and at CS₁₄ Fl_{3.2} by 64% in 2020 (Tables 5 and 6).

Across the crop growth stage tested in 2019, final sugar beet leaf area at Fl_{3.2} was on average 34% less than Fl_{0.2} and Fl_{0.8}. In 2020, the final leaf area across Fl_{0.4} and Fl_{0.8} was on average 44% less than Fl_{0.1} and Fl_{0.2}, and final leaf across Fl_{1.6} and Fl_{3.2} were on average 87% less than Fl_{0.4} and Fl_{0.8}, and 92% less than Fl_{0.1} and Fl_{0.2}. Across flaming intensities tested, sugar beet plants treated at CS₁₀ in 2020 also possessed a final leaf area that was on average 51% less than plants treated at CS₁₂ and CS₁₄. Across growth stages tested, in 2019, total sugar beet biomass at Fl_{3.2} was on average 36% less than Fl_{0.8}. In 2020, total biomass across Fl_{0.8}, Fl_{1.6}, and Fl_{3.2} were on average 73% less than Fl_{0.1} and Fl_{0.2}. Across flaming intensities tested, in 2019, sugar beet plants treated at CS₁₂ possessed a total biomass that was on average 25% less than plants treated at CS₁₄ and CS₁₆; in 2020, total biomass at CS₁₂ was 28% less than CS₁₄, and CS₁₀ was 42% and 58% less than CS₁₂ and CS₁₄, respectively.

Sugar beet mortality was 25% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.2}, 75% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.4}, and 100% at CS₁₀ Fl_{0.8}, CS₁₀ Fl_{1.6}, and CS₁₀ Fl_{3.2} in 2020 (data not shown). In 2020, 25% of plants were killed at CS₁₂ Fl_{0.8}, and 50% and 75% of plants were killed at CS₁₂ Fl_{1.6} in 2019 and 2020, respectively. Across site years, 100% of plants were killed at CS₁₂ Fl_{3.2} and a 75% sugar beet mortality rate at CS₁₄ Fl_{3.2} in 2020. A 100% survival rate was observed across all other treatments.

Flaming Distance

The average maximum temperatures achieved at the center of the sugar beet plants during treatment for each flaming distance studied were 132.5°C (±8.8) at FD_{0.0}, 118.4°C (±18.0) at FD_{0.5}, 130.6°C (±10.1) at FD_{1.0}, 116.9°C (±11.8) at FD_{1.5}, 120.7°C (±29.3) at FD_{2.0}, 97.6°C (±15.3) at FD_{2.5}, 42.6°C (±7.6) at FD_{3.0}, 33.5°C (±1.7) at FD_{3.5}, 42.5°C (±7.4) at FD_{4.0}. When each of the EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE} treatments were compared to the untreated control (FD_{CTRL}), the following contrasts were significant ($p < 0.05$). Final sugar beet leaf area was reduced by 95% at FD_{0.0} and 43% at FD_{1.0} (Figure 3, Table 7). Total sugar beet biomass was reduced by 85% at FD_{0.0} and 35% at FD_{1.0} (Figure 3, Table 7). Sugar beet root biomass (g) was reduced by 100% at FD_{0.0}, 41% at FD_{0.5}, and 51% at FD_{1.0}. Sugar beet shoot biomass (g) was reduced by 67% at FD_{0.0}. Sugar beet mortality was 88% at FD_{0.0}, 25% at FD_{0.5}, and 13% at FD_{1.0}; a 100% survival rate was observed across all other treatments (data not shown).

Discussion

Hoeing Distance

The majority of sugar beets that experienced a direct hit with the hoeing simulator (HD_0) were either killed or significantly damaged. Across affected treatments, total sugar beet biomass at HD_0 was 58 to 95% less than that of the untreated control (HD_{CTRL}). The only instance whereby HD_0 did not significantly reduce total biomass or final leaf area was when hoeing was performed at CS_{10} in 2019. While none of the sugar beets receiving direct cultivation at cotyledon stage in 2019 were killed, forking of the taproot (also known as root bifurcation) was observed among all plants in this category. In fact, across all crop growth stages evaluated, the survival rate of sugar beets receiving a direct hit with the hoe (HD_0) ranged from 0% to 75%, and taproot forking was observed in all surviving plants. Root forking is likely to have resulted from damage imparted to, or decapitation of, the root apical meristem during cultivation. Forked taproots in sugar beet significantly reduce crop quality and value. In addition, forked beets cling readily to the soil and are therefore more difficult to clean upon processing; forking in sugar beets may also result in greater soil loss at harvest (Ruyschaert et al., 2004). Melander et al. (2000) also noted the presence of forking among transplanted sugar beets cultivated with weed harrows or torsion weeders; although, it is suggested that forking could have been caused by rearing sugar beet seedlings as transplants. In the present study, all sugar beets were reared in containers, but forking was observed only among plants receiving HD_0 in $EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}$, suggesting that cultivation damage is responsible.

While the destructive consequences resulting from direct cultivation are not unexpected, results affirm the importance of avoiding collision during intra-row hoeing. Thus, the accuracy of intra-row hoeing machines is critical if attempting to cultivate in close proximity to crop plants. Kunz et al. (2015) identifies the need for research into both the optimal operating distance of hoeing blades relative to crop plants and the accuracy of precision cultivation equipment. The present study addresses the former request, and results emphasize the need for additional research pertaining to the latter request. The objective assessment of intelligent intra-row weeding machines capable of operating across early crop growth stages is necessary to define optimal intra-row hoeing distances within direct seeded crops. Machleb et al. (2020) provides a summary of mean guidance errors for both GNSS-navigation and machine-vision-based cultivation systems; of those reporting intra-row cultivator accuracy during field operation, errors of ± 0.6 to 2.9 cm were reported at forward speeds of 0.79 to 1.87 km h⁻¹ (Nørremark et al., 2008; Nørremark et al., 2012; Pérez-Ruiz et al., 2012). Notably, variability in intra-row crop spacing (Nørremark et al., 2012), heightened weed pressure (Fennimore et al., 2017; Lian et al., 2013), increasing intra-row crop density (Nørremark et al., 2008), and increasing forward speed (Nørremark et al., 2008; Pérez-Ruiz et al., 2012) all negatively affect intra-row hoeing accuracy.

The incidence of survival among young sugar beets receiving direct cultivation and their resulting loss of quality also represents important information for practitioners who may wish to employ automated intra-row cultivators with the concurrent goals of removing intra-row weeds and thinning intra-row sugar beets densities. Under these circumstances, results indicate that direct cultivation may not always have the desired effect of crop removal, thus, introducing the potential for leaving behind damaged crop plants of lesser quality. However, it is suspected that this issue can likely be resolved via tool adjustment. The present study maintained hoeing depth at 2 cm from the soil's surface across all treatments. Cultivating at a shallower depth may have resulted in higher mortality at HD₀, either by undercutting roots more shallowly or by segmenting roots and shoots completely, in both cases, decreasing the survival rate of sugar beet plants.

Across experimental years and crop stages tested, 100% of sugar beets survived hoeing when implemented at distances ≥ 1 cm without reducing sugar beet final leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, or total biomass. This information is highly relevant to manufacturers of automated intra-row cultivators, who provided these results, may aim to develop tools capable of accurately operating 1 cm from crop plants at CS₁₀, CS₁₂, and CS₁₄ without reducing crop stand or yield. The results of Nørremark et al. (2008) indicate that accurate intra-row hoeing 1 cm from crop plants may be possible; hoeing errors, whereby undesired hoeing occurred < 1 cm from crop plants, were reported as occurring in only 18 out of 1224 observations. As intra-row hoes capable of accurately cultivating 1 cm from crop plants become available, it will be necessary to affirm or refute the results of the present study under field conditions. Dependent upon soil conditions and hoe design, soil throw and incidental burial of the crop may be of concern, especially if cultivating very close to the crop while it is small.

Across site years, conflicting results were observed regarding sugar beet tolerance to hoeing across early growth stages. In 2019, crop stage at time of hoeing significantly affected root biomass, with sugar beets treated at the cotyledon stage having 12% larger roots on average compared to plants treated at the two- and four-leaf stage. This effect was primarily driven by a high survival rate of cotyledon stage sugar beets receiving a direct hit with the hoe. It was speculated that tolerance to direct hoeing could be attributed to plant flexibility and small crop size at the cotyledon stage; however, results from 2020 refute this notion. In 2020, direct hoeing CS₁₀ and CS₁₂ had a more significant adverse effect on crop growth parameters compared to CS₁₄; results are therefore inconclusive.

Flaming Intensity

Flaming should be avoided altogether when sugar beets are at the cotyledon growth stage. Across flaming intensities investigated, final leaf area and total biomass at CS10 were reduced by 51% on average compared to other growth stages tested. While no adverse effects on sugar beet growth were observed when cotyledon stage plants were exposed to a propane dose of 0.19 kg km^{-1} (Table 2), weed mortality at this flaming intensity may be too low to justify treatment (Sivesind et al., 2009). At the cotyledon stage, sugar beets are particularly vulnerable to lethal damages resulting from flaming because the above-ground apical meristem is highly exposed. As the crop develops, additional layers of leaves form a rosette, surrounding the apical meristem, further insulating it from damage during flaming.

As expected, increasing flaming intensity corresponded with increasing crop damages, and sugar beets became more tolerant to flaming as they advanced in growth stage. Direct flaming in sugar beet may be permissible at the two-leaf stage and on if flame intensity is well controlled. No negative effects on sugar beet growth were observed when propane dose was $\leq 0.74 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the two-leaf growth stage, $\leq 1.49 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the four-leaf growth stage, and $\leq 5.95 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the six-leaf growth stage (Table 2).

Dose-response curves to flaming intensity for common weed species have been described in experiments by Sivesind et al. (2009) and Ascard (1994; 1995). Because of differences in methodology and equipment, definitive conclusions should not be made by cross-referencing the flaming tolerance of sugar beet, reported by the present study, and the weed response to flaming, reported by previous works. However, the approximation of weed control possible across flaming intensities studied is highly relevant. A propane dose of 0.74 kg km^{-1} (tolerated by sugar beet at and above two-leaf stage) controlled 50% of redroot amaranth (*Amaranthus retroflexus* L.) up to the two-leaf stage, lambsquarters (*Chenopodium album* L.) up to the four-leaf stage, and shepherd's purse (*Capsella bursa-pastoris* [L.] Medik.) at the cotyledon stage (Sivesind et al., 2009). A propane dose of 1.49 kg km^{-1} (tolerated by sugar beet at and above the four-leaf stage) controlled 95% of *A. retroflexus* at the cotyledon stage, *C. album* up to the four-leaf stage, and *C. bursa-pastoris* at the cotyledon stage (Sivesind et al., 2009). Finally, a propane dose of 5.95 kg km^{-1} (tolerated by sugar beet at and above the four-leaf stage) controlled 95% of *A. retroflexus* and *C. album*, *C. bursa-pastoris* up to the four-leaf, six-leaf, and five-leaf stage, respectively (Sivesind et al., 2009). Results suggest that sugar beet may be more tolerant to flaming than some common annual broadleaf weeds; thus, the potential for direct flaming at intensities appropriate to the crop's growth stage exists. Establishing a false or stale seedbed would also delay weed emergence relative to crop emergence (Mohler, 2001), producing weeds that are delayed developmentally relative to the crop and increasing within-

row flaming efficacy. Further research on intra-row flaming in direct-seeded sugar beet is suggested to determine the level of weed control attainable across early growth stages in the field. However, heightened crop injury resulting from the re-direction of flames due to uneven soil may be a factor to contend with (Vanhala & Rahkonen, 1998).

Flaming Distance

Adverse effects on crop growth were not observed at flaming distances ≥ 1.5 cm. Results suggest that it is possible to selectively manage annual broadleaf weeds in the intra-row zone via flame weeding without sugar beet injury. Exposure to 2.0 seconds of flaming is equivalent to 3.72 kg km^{-1} of propane consumption (data not shown). Studies by Sivesind et al. (2009) indicate that exposing intra-row weeds to an equivalent flaming treatment may control 95% of *A. retroflexus* and *C. album*, *C. bursa-pastoris* up to the four-leaf, six-leaf, and five-leaf stage, respectively.

Future investigations should seek to aggregate results from $\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$ and $\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.DISTANCE}}$, exploring whether flaming intensity (propane dose) can be adjusted within the close-to-crop zone extending 1.5 cm to either side of sugar beet plants within the crop row. The successful adjustment of flaming intensity according to crop growth stage in the close-to-crop zone would enable selective weed control throughout the intra-row zone, maximizing efficacy and minimizing crop injury. Results from $\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$ suggests that flaming dose in the close-to-crop zone should not exceed 0.74 kg km^{-1} at the two-leaf growth stage, 1.49 kg km^{-1} at the four-leaf growth stage, and 5.95 kg km^{-1} at the six-leaf growth stage (Table 2). Combining automated intra-row hoeing, at distances as close as 1 cm from sugar beet plants, with selective flaming in the close-to-crop zone may also provide positive results.

It was expected that a 100% mortality rate would result from exposing sugar beet plants to 2.0 seconds of direct flaming at the two-leaf stage. This assumption was based on results from $\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$; however, only an 88% mortality rate was recorded at FD_0 . While the present study focuses on the crop's response to post-emergence flaming, pre-emergence flaming is a notable and effective method of intra-row weed control in sugar beet. A 30% to 47% reduction in weed density has been reported following pre-emergence flame weeding (Rasmussen, 2003; Rasmussen et al., 2011). Finally, average temperatures measured at the crop's center with a thermal imaging camera did not decline incrementally as flaming distance increased. The thermal camera appears to have done a better job measuring thermal energy in front of the flame ($\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.INTENSITY}}$) than the side of the flame ($\text{EXP}_{\text{FLAME.DISTANCE}}$). In either case, the achieved temperatures reported in the present study should be considered approximate. Vanhala and

Rahkonen (1998) describe an improved method for measuring achieved temperatures using thermocouples.

Conclusions

Sugar beet tolerance to hoeing and flame weeding across early crop growth stages, tool working distances, and intensities were evaluated. From the cotyledon stage to the four-leaf stage, hoeing could be performed as close as 1 cm from sugar beet plant centers before negative crop effects were observed. It is unclear, however, whether sugar beets become more or less sensitive to hoeing as the crop progresses through early growth stages. Direct flaming of sugar beet at the cotyledon stage is not advised at any intensity; though, flaming tolerance was observed to increase with crop growth stage. Direct flaming did not affect sugar beets when the propane dose was $\leq 0.74 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the two-leaf stage, $\leq 1.49 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the four-leaf stage, and $\leq 5.95 \text{ kg km}^{-1}$ at the six-leaf stage. Sugar beets at the two-leaf growth stage could withstand flaming at distances $\geq 1.5 \text{ cm}$ at a propane dose of 3.72 kg km^{-1} without causing damage. Results of the present study are highly relevant to informing the development and operation of automated intra-row weeding machines in direct seeded sugar beet. However, additional experimentation is necessary to confirm or refute results from this controlled environment study across various agricultural field settings.

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Conflicts of Interest

Authors Margaret R McCollough and Bo Melander declare no conflicts of interest. Frank Poulsen is the founder and CEO of F. Poulsen Engineering ApS., a manufacturer of intelligent automated intra-row weeding devices.

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Table 1. Summary of dates and crop growth stages when key operations were performed within EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE} and EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} trials in 2019 and 2020, and EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE} in 2021.

Experiment	Year	Experiment operations	Date	Sugar beet growth stage ^a
EXP _{HOE.DISTANCE}	2019	Sow sugar beets	15 July	–
		First hoeing treatment	22 July	10
		Second hoeing treatment	1 August	12
		Third hoeing treatment	7 August	14
		Harvest experiment	29–30 August	6–18
	2020	Sow sugar beets	16 July	–
		First hoeing treatment	28 July	10
		Second hoeing treatment	4 August	12
		Third hoeing treatment	11 August	14
		Harvest experiment	24–27 August	4–11
EXP _{FLAME.INTENSITY}	2019	Sow sugar beets	15 July	–
		First flame weeding treatment	30 July	12
		Second flame weeding treatment	8 August	14
		Third flame weeding treatment	13 August	16
		Harvest experiment	30–31 August	6–16
	2020	Sow sugar beets	16 July	–
		First flame weeding treatment	27 July	10
		Second flame weeding treatment	3 August	12
		Third flame weeding treatment	10 August	14
		Harvest experiment	21 August	4–10
EXP _{FLAME.DISTANCE}	2021	Sow sugar beets	22 April	–
		Flame weeding treatments	20 May	10–14
		Harvest experiment	15 June	6–13

^a Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) growth stages are reported according to Meier et al. (2001) BBCH decimal codes.

Table 2. EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY} and EXP_{FLAME.DISTANCE} treatments converted from flaming intensity (FI; 0.1 to 3.2 seconds of exposure to flame when flaming distance relative to the center of sugar beet plants is held constant at 2.0 cm) and flaming distance (FD; 0.0 to 4.0 cm flaming distance relative to the center of sugar beet plants when flaming duration is held constant at 2.0 seconds) to oxygen and propane fuel consumption per linear km of crop row (kg km⁻¹) when a 15 cm intra-row crop spacing assumed.

Experiment	Treatment	Propane	Oxygen
		consumption	consumption
		kg km ⁻¹	
EXP _{FLAME.INTENSITY}	FI _{0.1}	0.19	0.12
	FI _{0.2}	0.37	0.25
	FI _{0.4}	0.74	0.49
	FI _{0.8}	1.49	0.99
	FI _{1.6}	2.97	1.98
	FI _{3.2}	5.95	3.95
	FI _{CTRL}	0.00	0.00
EXP _{FLAME.DISTANCE}	FD _{0.0}	5.07	3.37
	FD _{0.5}	4.73	3.14
	FD _{1.0}	4.39	2.92
	FD _{1.5}	4.06	2.69
	FD _{2.0}	3.72	2.47
	FD _{2.5}	3.38	2.25
	FD _{3.0}	3.04	2.02
	FD _{3.5}	2.70	1.80
	FD _{4.0}	2.37	1.57
	FD _{CTRL}	0.00	0.00

Table 3. In 2019, sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to hoeing distance [0 (HD₀), 1 (HD₁), 2 (HD₂), 3 (HD₃), 4 (HD₄), and 5 (HD₅) cm] across early growth stages [cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), and four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄)]. Treatment effects on sugar beet final leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, and total biomass are shown. Least square means are presented. P-values associated with each mean result from contrasts made with an untreated control (FD_{CTRL}), * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), and *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001). Significant main effects (P < 0.05) are highlighted in bold text.

Treatment	Final leaf area		Root biomass ^a			Shoot biomass ^b			Total biomass ^a		
			Trans.	Back-trans.		Trans.	Back-trans.		Trans.	Back-trans.	
	cm ²		g			g					
CS ₁₀ HD ₀	203.4	0.9702	2.26	4.10	0.1344	0.77	4.83	0.2717	3.16	9.00	0.1405
CS ₁₀ HD ₁	220.7	0.7393	2.65	6.00	0.7626	0.78	5.06	0.3371	3.48	11.09	0.4239
CS ₁₀ HD ₂	190.8	0.7577	2.80	6.86	0.8494	0.77	4.90	0.2894	3.59	11.89	0.5796
CS ₁₀ HD ₃	180.5	0.5961	2.67	6.13	0.8215	0.85	6.03	0.6753	3.67	12.50	0.7114
CS ₁₀ HD ₄	197.1	0.8626	2.99	7.91	0.4522	0.90	6.90	0.9955	3.99	14.89	0.7557
CS ₁₀ HD ₅	144.5	0.1964	2.31	4.33	0.1799	0.64	3.37	0.0337 *	2.95	7.73	0.0560
CS ₁₂ HD ₀	97.1	0.0236 *	1.16	0.34	<0.0001 ***	0.22	0.64	<0.0001 ***	1.42	1.00	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₂ HD ₁	176.0	0.5320	2.41	4.83	0.3077	0.72	4.26	0.1408	3.21	9.30	0.1689
CS ₁₂ HD ₂	135.4	0.1379	2.55	5.50	0.5475	0.74	4.46	0.1813	3.39	10.52	0.3272
CS ₁₂ HD ₃	176.6	0.5400	2.65	6.03	0.7748	0.85	6.08	0.6943	3.63	12.16	0.6368
CS ₁₂ HD ₄	194.0	0.8112	2.29	4.22	0.1582	0.82	5.53	0.4912	3.34	10.14	0.2712
CS ₁₂ HD ₅	239.6	0.4612	2.79	6.76	0.8959	0.90	6.87	0.9954	3.87	13.95	0.9588
CS ₁₄ HD ₀	0.0	<0.0001 ***	1.00	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.22	0.68	<0.0001 ***	1.30	0.69	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₄ HD ₁	171.6	0.4721	2.87	7.26	0.6823	0.85	6.05	0.6829	3.82	13.63	0.9670
CS ₁₄ HD ₂	212.3	0.8781	2.73	6.45	0.9675	0.88	6.66	0.9157	3.77	13.21	0.8723
CS ₁₄ HD ₃	168.0	0.4628	2.49	5.22	0.4384	0.74	4.48	0.1862	3.28	9.76	0.2214
CS ₁₄ HD ₄	167.8	0.4240	2.48	5.17	0.4203	0.83	5.83	0.5990	3.52	11.38	0.4788
CS ₁₄ HD ₅	195.7	0.8388	2.41	4.81	0.3020	0.87	6.39	0.8125	3.53	11.47	0.4954
HD _{CTRL}	205.2		2.74	6.52		0.90	6.88		3.84	13.77	
ANOVA						P					
HD		0.0099			<0.0001			<0.0001			<0.0001
CS		0.1657			0.0369			0.2613			0.1611
HD*CS		0.0192			0.0237			0.0010			0.0070

^a Data underwent a square root (x+1) transformation before analysis. Transformed means (Trans.) are presented along with back-transformed means (Back-trans.). Percent change calculated between treatments and discussed throughout the text of the present article are calculated from back-transformed means.

^b Data underwent a log₁₀ (x+1) transformation before analysis. Transformed means (Trans.) are presented along with back-transformed means (Back-trans.). Percent change calculated between treatments and discussed throughout the text of the present article are calculated from back-transformed means.

Table 4. In 2020, sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to hoeing distance [0 (HD₀), 1 (HD₁), 2 (HD₂), 3 (HD₃), 4 (HD₄), and 5 (HD₅) cm] across early growth stages [cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), and four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄)]. Treatment effects on sugar beet final leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, and total biomass are shown. Least square means are presented. P-values associated with each mean result from contrasts made with an untreated control (FD_{CTRL}), * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), and *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001). Significant main effects (P < 0.05) are highlighted in bold text.

Treatment		Final leaf area		Root biomass		Shoot biomass ^a			Total biomass ^b		
						Trans.	Back-trans.		Trans.	Back-trans.	
		cm ²				g					
CS ₁₀	HD ₀	23	0.0005 ***	0.17	0.0061 **	0.05	0.12	0.0003 ***	1.14	0.29	0.0007 ***
CS ₁₀	HD ₁	78	0.3260	0.41	0.2970	0.21	0.63	0.5015	1.43	1.04	0.4020
CS ₁₀	HD ₂	98	0.9764	0.48	0.6541	0.25	0.79	0.9080	1.51	1.27	.9232
CS ₁₀	HD ₃	113	0.4325	0.77	0.0984	0.34	1.20	0.0629	1.73	1.98	0.0551
CS ₁₀	HD ₄	78	0.3426	0.46	0.5193	0.22	0.67	0.6213	1.46	1.12	0.5723
CS ₁₀	HD ₅	113	0.4276	0.51	0.7809	0.27	0.87	0.6192	1.54	1.38	0.8127
CS ₁₂	HD ₀	17	0.0002 ***	0.04	0.0004 ***	0.04	0.09	0.0001 ***	1.07	0.13	0.0001 ***
CS ₁₂	HD ₁	79	0.3517	0.41	0.3164	0.20	0.59	0.3731	1.41	1.00	0.3368
CS ₁₂	HD ₂	132	0.0924	0.60	0.6965	0.30	1.00	0.2816	1.61	1.60	0.3745
CS ₁₂	HD ₃	102	0.8077	0.57	0.8261	0.23	0.68	0.6735	1.50	1.26	0.8948
CS ₁₂	HD ₄	83	0.4628	0.44	0.4162	0.21	0.63	0.4848	1.44	1.06	0.4452
CS ₁₂	HD ₅	100	0.9098	0.53	0.8946	0.25	0.76	0.9911	1.51	1.29	0.9769
CS ₁₄	HD ₀	39	0.0054 **	0.19	0.0104 *	0.13	0.35	0.0258 *	1.24	0.54	0.0125 *
CS ₁₄	HD ₁	102	0.8127	0.60	0.6624	0.27	0.86	0.6705	1.57	1.45	0.6486
CS ₁₄	HD ₂	94	0.8567	0.53	0.9108	0.24	0.72	0.8257	1.50	1.25	0.8571
CS ₁₄	HD ₃	89	0.6905	0.57	0.8613	0.25	0.77	0.9970	1.53	1.33	0.9307
CS ₁₄	HD ₄	93	0.8337	0.57	0.8219	0.23	0.71	0.8001	1.51	1.29	0.9571
CS ₁₄	HD ₅	87	0.6028	0.43	0.3724	0.21	0.62	0.4792	1.43	1.05	0.4234
	HD _{CTRL}	97		0.54		0.25	0.77		1.52	1.30	
ANOVA						P					
HD		<0.0001		<0.0001		<0.0001			<0.0001		
CS		0.9834		0.6102		0.5488			0.5512		
HD*CS		0.3690		0.4920		0.1775			0.2453		

^a Data underwent a log₁₀ (x+1) transformation before analysis. Transformed means (Trans.) are presented along with back-transformed means (Back-trans.). Percent change calculated between treatments and discussed throughout the text of the present article are calculated from back-transformed means.

^b Data underwent a square root (x+1) transformation before analysis. Transformed means (Trans.) are presented along with back-transformed means (Back-trans.). Percent change calculated between treatments and discussed throughout the text of the present article are calculated from back-transformed means.

Table 5. In 2019, sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to flaming intensities [0.1 (FI_{0.1}), 0.2 (FI_{0.2}), 0.4 (FI_{0.4}), 0.8 (FI_{0.8}), 1.6 (FI_{1.6}), and 3.2 (FI_{3.2}) seconds] across early growth stages [two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄), and six leaves unfolded (CS₁₆)] when flaming distance is held constant. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, and total biomass are shown. Least square means are presented. P-values associated with each mean result from contrasts made with an untreated control (FDCTRL), * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), and *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001). Significant main effects (P < 0.05) are highlighted in bold text.

Treatment	Final leaf area		Root biomass		Shoot biomass		Total biomass	
	cm ²				g			
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.1}	163.1	0.1676	6.15	0.3392	5.75	0.1559	11.9	0.2093
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.2}	143.6	0.5063	4.74	0.9272	3.09	0.2663	7.8	0.5557
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.4}	146.8	0.4345	5.14	0.8361	4.09	0.8675	9.2	0.9627
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.8}	134.1	0.7544	6.09	0.3620	4.88	0.5534	11.0	0.4007
CS ₁₂ FI _{1.6}	56.0	0.0119 *	1.26	0.0093 **	1.62	0.0145 *	2.9	0.0061 **
CS ₁₂ FI _{3.2}	0.0	<0.0001 ***	1.77	0.0245 *	0.04	0.0002 ***	1.8	0.0015 **
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.1}	107.7	0.5046	4.13	0.5830	3.68	0.5774	7.8	0.5473
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.2}	139.4	0.6114	6.26	0.3016	5.45	0.2593	11.7	0.2422
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.4}	137.7	0.6547	5.74	0.5150	4.10	0.8858	8.8	0.8841
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.8}	146.0	0.4520	6.54	0.2157	5.32	0.3144	11.9	0.2163
CS ₁₄ FI _{1.6}	109.8	0.5559	4.37	0.7150	3.81	0.6698	8.2	0.6694
CS ₁₄ FI _{3.2}	131.7	0.8233	5.41	0.6847	4.40	0.8919	9.8	0.7541
CS ₁₆ FI _{0.1}	96.7	0.2845	5.48	0.6482	5.03	0.4667	10.5	0.5309
CS ₁₆ FI _{0.2}	140.3	0.5872	6.35	0.2694	5.28	0.3328	11.6	0.2555
CS ₁₆ FI _{0.4}	120.9	0.8587	2.74	0.1177	3.77	0.6423	6.5	0.2373
CS ₁₆ FI _{0.8}	139.6	0.6061	5.44	0.6671	4.66	0.7030	10.1	0.6562
CS ₁₆ FI _{1.6}	136.5	0.6882	6.99	0.1165	5.62	0.1997	12.6	0.1164
CS ₁₆ FI _{3.2}	146.9	0.4321	5.71	0.5282	3.92	0.7459	9.6	0.8171
FI _{CTRL}	125.7		4.86		4.26		9.1	
ANOVA					P			
FI		0.0068		0.0946		0.0065		0.0165
CS		0.0719		0.0433		0.0028		0.0084
FI*CS		<0.0001		0.0029		0.0027		0.0011

Table 6. In 2020, sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to flaming intensities [0.1 (FI_{0.1}), 0.2 (FI_{0.2}), 0.4 (FI_{0.4}), 0.8 (FI_{0.8}), 1.6 (FI_{1.6}), and 3.2 (FI_{3.2}) seconds] across early growth stages [cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), and four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄)] when flaming distance is held constant. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, and total biomass are shown. Least square means are presented. P-values associated with each mean result from contrasts made with an untreated control (FDCTRL), * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), and *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001). Significant main effects (P < 0.05) are highlighted in bold text.

Treatment	Final leaf area		Root biomass ^a			Shoot biomass		Total biomass	
	cm ²		Trans.	Back-trans.	g				
CS ₁₀ FI _{0.1}	105.90	0.4820	0.177	0.502	0.7771	0.891	0.8260	1.395	0.9816
CS ₁₀ FI _{0.2}	60.82	0.0254 *	0.113	0.297	0.1181	0.629	0.0666	0.941	0.0769
CS ₁₀ FI _{0.4}	0.47	<0.0001 ***	0.001	0.003	<0.0001 ***	0.019	<0.0001 ***	0.022	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₀ FI _{0.8}	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.000	0.000	<0.0001 ***	0.005	<0.0001 ***	0.005	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₀ FI _{1.6}	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.000	0.000	<0.0001 ***	0.001	<0.0001 ***	0.001	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₀ FI _{3.2}	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.000	0.000	<0.0001 ***	0.004	<0.0001 ***	0.004	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.1}	80.47	0.3275	0.140	0.382	0.4396	0.684	0.1340	1.075	0.2073
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.2}	92.85	0.8717	0.118	0.313	0.1584	0.726	0.2144	1.053	0.1787
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.4}	84.28	0.4664	0.151	0.415	0.6343	0.783	0.3724	1.204	0.4435
CS ₁₂ FI _{0.8}	41.91	0.0008 ***	0.067	0.168	0.0051 **	0.393	0.0014 **	0.569	0.0019 **
CS ₁₂ FI _{1.6}	6.85	<0.0001 ***	0.009	0.021	<0.0001 ***	0.139	<0.0001 ***	0.161	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₂ FI _{3.2}	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.005	0.012	<0.0001 ***	0.009	<0.0001 ***	0.022	<0.0001 ***
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.1}	80.41	0.3258	0.129	0.345	0.2654	0.740	0.2479	1.097	0.2389
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.2}	99.75	0.7670	0.170	0.480	0.9255	0.891	0.8276	1.384	0.9469
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.4}	86.48	0.5596	0.154	0.427	0.7128	0.699	0.1591	1.143	0.3163
CS ₁₄ FI _{0.8}	78.90	0.2794	0.136	0.368	0.3696	0.651	0.0890	1.027	0.1483
CS ₁₄ FI _{1.6}	32.53	0.0001 ***	0.071	0.176	0.0065 **	0.472	0.0060 **	0.657	0.0052 **
CS ₁₄ FI _{3.2}	0.00	<0.0001 ***	0.017	0.040	0.0001 ***	0.329	0.0004 ***	0.369	0.0002 ***
FI _{CTRL}	95.29		0.167	0.469		0.926		1.401	
ANOVA					P				
FI		<0.0001		0.0001		<0.0001		<0.0001	
CS		<0.0001		<0.0001		<0.0001		<0.0001	
FI*CS		<0.0001		0.0031		0.0044		0.0050	

^a Data underwent a log₁₀ (x+1) transformation before analysis. Transformed means (Trans.) are presented along with back-transformed means (Back-trans.). Percent change calculated between treatments and discussed throughout the text of the present article are calculated from back-transformed means.

Table 7. In 2021, sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to flaming distance [0.0 (FD_{0.0}), 0.5 (FD_{0.5}), 1.0 (FD_{1.0}), 1.5 (FD_{1.5}), 2.0 (FD_{2.0}), 2.5 (FD_{2.5}), 3.0 (FD_{3.0}), 3.5 (FD_{3.5}), and 4.0 (FD_{4.0}) cm] when crop growth stage and flaming duration are held constant. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area, root biomass, shoot biomass, and total biomass are shown. Least square means are presented. P-values associated with each mean result from contrasts made with an untreated control (FD_{CTRL}), * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), and *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001). Significant main effects (P < 0.05) are highlighted in bold text.

Treatment	Final leaf area			Root biomass		Shoot biomass		Total biomass	
	cm ²					g			
FD _{0.0}	5.1	< 0.0001	***	- 0.015	< 0.0001	***	0.181	< 0.0001	***
FD _{0.5}	75.9	0.2582		0.343	0.0423	*	0.478	0.3603	0.82
FD _{1.0}	54.7	0.0208	*	0.281	0.0109	*	0.457	0.2408	0.74
FD _{1.5}	157.8	0.0006	***	0.856	0.0174	*	0.891	0.0001	***
FD _{2.0}	127.2	0.0748		0.710	0.2618		0.728	0.0381	*
FD _{2.5}	152.3	0.0022	**	0.734	0.1936		0.838	0.0012	**
FD _{3.0}	112.3	0.3329		0.632	0.6428		0.656	0.2083	1.29
FD _{3.5}	144.2	0.0064	**	0.830	0.0310	*	0.799	0.0036	**
FD _{4.0}	129.7	0.0542		0.743	0.1594		0.756	0.0162	*
FD _{CTRL}	95.5			0.579			0.553		1.13
ANCOVA						P			
FD		< 0.0001			< 0.0001			< 0.0001	
Leaf area (cm ²) ^a		< 0.0001			< 0.0001			< 0.0001	

^a Leaf area (cm²) on the day of implementing flaming treatments.

Fig. 1 Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to hoeing distance [0 (HD₀), 1 (HD₁), 2 (HD₂), 3 (HD₃), 4 (HD₄), and 5 (HD₅) cm] across early growth stages [cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), and four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄)]. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area in 2019 (a) and 2020 (b) are shown, as well as treatment effects on total sugar beet biomass in 2019 (c) and 2020 (d). Final leaf area figures (a, b) present least square means and standard errors. Total biomass figures (c, d) present back-transformed least square means; data underwent a square root (x+1) transformation prior to analysis. Results that differ significantly from the untreated control (FD_{CTRL}) are denoted with * (P = 0.0500–0.0100), ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), or *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001).

Fig. 2 Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to flaming intensity [0.1 (F_{0.1}), 0.2 (F_{0.2}), 0.4 (F_{0.4}), 0.8 (F_{0.8}), 1.6 (F_{1.6}), and 3.2 (F_{3.2}) seconds] across early growth stages [cotyledons unfolded (CS₁₀), two leaves unfolded (CS₁₂), four leaves unfolded (CS₁₄), and six leaves unfolded (CS₁₆)] when flaming distance is held constant. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area in 2019 (a) and 2020 (b) are shown, as well as treatment effects on total sugar beet biomass in 2019 (c) and 2020 (d). Least square means and standard errors are presented. Results that differ significantly from the untreated control (FD_{CTRL}) are denoted with * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), or *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001).

Fig. 3 Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) response to flaming distance [0.0 (FD_{0.0}), 0.5 (FD_{0.5}), 1.0 (FD_{1.0}), 1.5 (FD_{1.5}), 2.0 (FD_{2.0}), 2.5 (FD_{2.5}), 3.0 (FD_{3.0}), 3.5 (FD_{3.5}), and 4.0 (FD_{4.0}) cm] when crop growth stage and flaming duration are held constant. Treatment effects on final sugar beet leaf area (a) are shown, as well as treatment effects on total sugar beet biomass (b). Least square means and standard errors are presented. Results that differ significantly from the untreated control (FD_{CTRL}) are denoted with * (P = 0.0500–0.0100) ** (P = 0.0100–0.0010), or *** (P = 0.0010–0.0001).

6.4.1 Supplementary Information

Supplementary Video 1. A depiction of the experimental set-up employed to implement hoeing treatments in $EXP_{HOE.DISTANCE}$, including the hoeing simulator.

Supplementary Video 2. A depiction of the experimental set-up employed to implement flaming treatments in $EXP_{FLAME.INTENSITY}$, including the flaming simulator and thermal imaging camera.